

Developing cross-sectoral cooperation for youth employability in the Western Balkans

ERASMUS-YOUTH-2021-CB

Training Handbook

The training handbook is also available in online format at <https://croco4u.startupszeged.org/>

The training handbook is part of the project "Developing cross-sectoral cooperation for youth employability in the Western Balkans" and supported by the European Commission.

Introduction

Case studies, situational games and structured experiential exercises are used to ensure effective learning and a high level of experience. The case studies and exercises are based on our experience in advising start-ups and training young start-up entrepreneurs.

Alongside these are situations we have put together, which we have found to be particularly effective in transforming behaviours and deepening self-awareness. Our training is based on the principles of assertive communication and the use of related communication techniques and tools.

The training builds on the strength of the group, and accordingly relies on participants to open up, share their experiences and ideas, and be more open than usual. Therefore, the primary task of our training is to create and maintain a safe atmosphere in which participants can do this comfortably.

We also emphasise that participants should learn not only from the trainers but also from each other, get professional feedback on their ideas and develop the relationships that they can use to implement their ideas and build their businesses.

Professional opinion is divided on the importance of soft skills in business. Some attach an importance to them that overshadows the importance of hard skills, others see them as a necessary evil.

Are soft skills important for entrepreneurship, to get an innovative, scalable idea off the ground and to develop well, to make a start-up successful? The statement that "being an entrepreneur today is a bit different from what it used to be" can often seem like a cop-out. You want to work with and for your customers, you want to show them that it's not just a professional, business relationship. You want to build on the products and all the services, you don't want to force them on people, you want your customers to see you, not just your product and you want to show that you are ready to work with them. You need to make them feel comfortable and familiar with what you have to offer.

Another big difference between start-ups and old-style businesses, the old-style businesses were actually based on a very standard business plan that the owners and all employees had to follow exactly. There was not a lot of risk taking and only a minority of companies took the risk to implement an idea or method that could even produce a critical result. Today, however, as a young entrepreneur, there are many areas that are risky and risk-taking can be said to be a necessity.

Soft skills for business can be divided into four categories: organisational skills, planning and strategic skills, communication skills and people skills (leadership skills). Therefore, in order to improve any given skill, you can think about which category it falls into and thus make it easier to come up with a strategy that will work better.

In 2006, the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union adopted a resolution on key competences for lifelong learning, which was reconsidered in 2018 in the light of experience and reformulated as follows.

- Literacy competences
- Multilingualism competences
- Mathematics and science competences,
- Technology and engineering (STEM) competences
- Digital competence
- Personal, social and learning competences
- Citizenship competences
- Entrepreneurial competence
- Cultural awareness and expression

Among these, we will examine those that will or may be linked to those presented in other aspects of our training material. It is worth drawing a parallel between the soft skills generally accepted in the start-up world and the competences that are also essential for lifelong learning.

Communication in a foreign language - paraphrased as "foreign language" terminology - does not always reflect the wide range of linguistic situations and circumstances that individuals encounter, but it is nowadays indispensable, especially in start-ups. It is also an important tool for scaling up, but market opportunities are severely limited if we as entrepreneurs and idea owners do not consider this area important.

Since most startups are technology-based, it is clear that STEM - an acronym for science and technology disciplines (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) and related courses - is a catch-all term. It was originally included under the heading "Mathematical Competences", but needs to be interpreted more broadly. Digital literacy is also intrinsically linked to this definition, with the idea that even if an idea is not specifically based on digital technology, these tools and technologies are now inevitable in its implementation.

Learning competences have been included under the heading "personal, social and learning competences", as there are many links in these areas and they are considered as one of the core competences for further learning and learning to learn in terms of developing soft skills. This could represent an important change in the way learning support is delivered. It is important that, in addition to our own development, we also support our team members to be aware of their personal and social development, so that they understand this as a core competency area throughout the project.

The social and civic competences have been renamed "civic competence". This allows for a broad reflection on active citizenship, participation and solidarity experiences and emphasises the value of the following in the field of civic learning. This includes organisational as well as employer branding, and CSR - Corporate Social Responsibility - whereby companies take into account the interests of society.

Initiative and entrepreneurship have been added to the renewed list as "entrepreneurial competence", which shows how important an element this is for self-development, not only for start-ups. Entrepreneurship thus encompasses the ability to take initiative, to seize opportunities and to turn ideas into action that has cultural, social or financial value for others.

Soft skill: Entrepreneurial thinking - Planning and strategic skills (MODULE 1-2)

Innovative leaders and entrepreneurs know that "Soft Skills" are the hardest to master, but the most important for their business. Soft Skills are the skills, habits and behaviors that differentiate us as professionals and make the difference in our ability to achieve a project goal, resolve conflict and interact with others. Knowledge and practice in leadership, efficiency, team management, sales and communication skills are among the most valuable tools for entrepreneurs.

- How many hours (minutes) do you complete the given unit: 8 hours

Module 1 - A	The importance of Soft Skills for entrepreneurs
Block 1 title	Becoming a Startupper
Block 2 title	Developing our skills - Creativity
Module 1 - B	Entrepreneurship skills - Soft Skills
Block 1 title	Combining soft skills
Block 2 title	Creativity
Block 3 title	Learning from feedback
Welcome Note	<p>Welcome!</p> <p>In this module we will take a look at a specific technique of peacebuilding and change-making: Becoming a Startupper</p> <p>The assignments shall help you to develop a good understanding for the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the power of Management, ownership approach? - Why is self-awareness important in business? - How can we improve our soft skills through feedback? <p>Enjoy the module!</p>
Task 1 - Title	Competences to start a business
Task 1 - Instruction text	To get a picture of soft skills' importance, we can ask ourselves what would happen if we did not develop our persuasive and

	leadership skills, delegate responsibly or communicate well in person and online when implementing our ideas.
Task 1 - Links (if needed)	Became a startupper
Block 1 - Resources	

The importance of Soft Skills for entrepreneurs

Block 1 - Becoming a Startupper

The ability to start new businesses, especially start-ups based on innovative elements, requires the continuous learning and development of these skills (EU principle of life long learning). This is a necessary approach to be able to continuously build and develop our projects. Just as it is not enough that the business plan prepared at the beginning does not hold up to the constant changes and challenges, so in self-development and self-learning, the entrepreneur needs something more if he wants to be successful.

Every day we add new knowledge to our "baggage", but it is important to have the best soft skills from the starting point that will help us develop our project, make us a credible and effective leader in our team. We need a synthesis of the classic leadership skills - such as autonomy, accountability, critical vision - and the integration of the soft-skills that are more prominent in the startup ecosystem - credibility, accountability, resilience.

Training exercise: *Individual completion of the Belbin group dynamics test and analysis of the results. After a presentation of the test and the use of the method, the group discusses why it is important to consider the combination of work styles, competences and values that emerge in group work.*

Tools for the exercise: *Belbin Group Dynamics Test Printed, Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

As an entrepreneur, businessman or manager, it is not only the concept we want to use, but also the new elements and approaches required by the changes. Developing these skills will allow us to create the right environment to promote our project, to keep our team together, and to represent our business in a strong and convincing way.

"Training and learning are the raw materials of an entrepreneur. Much more than money or ideas" - Mike Cobian, General Partner, The Valley Venture Capital

We need to know what our strengths are and how we can develop them, what our weaknesses are and how to be prepared to properly address or prevent the resulting challenges. We need to recognise what makes us unique, different from our competitors or from the wider market. An entrepreneurial mindset is another way of learning, both a tool and a motivator, and we definitely need to develop this skill, not only in the hard elements but also in the soft areas.

An entrepreneurial mindset implies that the leader takes a proactive approach to the challenges that arise or are expected in the organization. He or she must be able to help employees manage stress of all kinds, as countless research and personal experiences show how stress, whether individual or team-related, can lead to serious performance degradation. Social, business and generational changes in mindset are also increasingly highlighting the importance of a pleasant working environment, a reliable leader, inspiring tasks and a predictable future. To create this positive atmosphere, a leader must not only be good at the skills - hard or soft - needed to achieve this, but also exude it through his or her whole personality. Today, it is no longer enough for a leader to have a local presence and a positive attitude during meetings at work, as communication at work and in the community extends to all periods and areas of life, through constant and anytime access. The leader's online footprint, presence and opinions are also accessible and influential for his/her colleagues and the teams working together on the project. There are countless examples every day that show how a badly worded or ill-timed post can cause serious damage to a project, to an organization, but also to team cohesion and staff commitment.

Block 2 - Developing our skills - Creativity

The entrepreneur must be aware of these laws and be ready to develop the soft skills needed in this area in a continuous and conscious way. However, this alone is not sufficient if one of the most important of these skills, the managerial approach, does not underpin this whole process and if it does not receive sufficient attention and energy to nurture and strengthen it.

It is worth taking a critical look at aspects and content of the classic literature on managerial thinking, as user habits and customer expectations have changed in recent years, both in terms of the social image of service providers and their social responsibility.

A central idea of Ajzen's theory of planned behavior is the distinction between intention and action. A serious entrepreneurial intention does not imply that the action will actually take place, i.e. that the start-up will take place. Intention is a function of attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control. Without serious intention, no actual action can be expected. However, actual action is influenced by objectively available factors such as access to the necessary resources, opportunities (money, time, etc.) required to achieve the intention.

There is a positive correlation between the attitude towards entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurial intention. The more favourable an individual's attitude towards entrepreneurship, the higher his/her intention to start a business is likely to be. A supportive social environment and social norms can also have a positive impact on the intention to start a business. The more an individual perceives that his/her environment is positive towards his/her start-up ideas, the more likely he/she is to show the intention to start his/her own business.

Training exercise: *What was the moment, the motivation that made them think they would invest time, energy and money in this. Make them aware that it will be important to recall these thoughts and feelings in future challenges, because they will help them overcome the difficulties. This exercise is the first step to practising presenting their thoughts, preparing them for the challenges of presenting a pitch.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers, DIXIT game cards*

The power of social media to shape opinion and the proliferation of dynamic communication tools, the dramatic rise of smart devices has changed the way entrepreneurs think about customers and buyers. People don't just buy things and services, it is increasingly important to think about and check other people's opinions, experiences, possible social and environmental implications before doing so. Today, when an entrepreneur starts a business or project, he or she needs to be aware that customers want to know that they can trust the company that makes the products and the people behind the processes. If you want your start-up to be successful, you need to make sure that you create a relationship between you and your customers based on a viable, people-centred, socially responsible approach. Don't make the mistake of thinking of your customers as just a network you've created, they're not a faceless mass. As customer habits and needs change, the role of communities has

become stronger and the entrepreneur who fails to keep up with this trend will be left behind in terms of market trends.

Entrepreneurial skills - Soft Skills

We will summarise the soft skills that are most important for the entrepreneur and develop them in relation to the areas that are most relevant for startups. It's not about becoming perfect in one area and then moving on to the next, but rather about having the right mix of the important elements.

Block 1 - Combining soft skills

One of the most important elements related to this area is initiative. Being proactive is a complex concept and can be interpreted in many different ways. It means understanding new challenges, their market potential, being flexible to new situations, coordinating resources and ideas, and using innovative methods to implement them. Taking the initiative is essential to take the first step, to start a business or to launch an idea. Without this soft skill, it is very difficult to become an entrepreneur, to work independently, to take the first step, to be adventurous and to be willing to adopt new methods.

Without sales, investors, partners, there is no business and to be effective in these we need to negotiate in countless ways and times. It is also true that methods, trends and tendencies are changing dynamically. Not only do the channels of communication evolve on an almost daily basis, but so do the rules of business etiquette, including, for example, business dress, and customs. The emergence and prominence of pitch, social media and blockchain technology, the use of which must be taken into account, but also the traditional methods, values and skills

The use of networking skills has changed and is changing a lot today. Personal networking systems are forcing entrepreneurs to rethink their approach with the proliferation of social media, Web 2 applications and methods. However, it is also true here that the classic methods cannot be forgotten, and that the rules of personal contact and persuasive behaviour must be learned and practised. This includes good communication - including meta, verbal, non-verbal areas - and knowledge of the rules of dress, respect for social - and culture-dependent - etiquette. At the same time, online channels and social spaces have developed their own set of rules and regulations, which, because of their differences, have made this area even more complex. Networking means expanding the professional network of contacts, and without contacts

without networking there is no business, and this is true even if the changing tools and platforms give the impression that it can be left out of the process or completely automated. Networking events continue to be an important element in the development of our business, and here too the mosaic of change across age groups, cultures, countries and many other factors is of particular importance.

It is vital for an entrepreneur to be able to use effective communication tools to get his ideas across, to present his products, services and plans to his peers, employees, business partners, investors and customers. The entrepreneur must be aware of the importance of effective communication as a crucial element of business strategy and competitiveness improvement, which has a major impact on all other activities and even on other soft skills. To make our communication effective and to be able to continuously improve, we need to develop a more comprehensive vision. Here too, the dynamics of our social and business environment are such that we must occasionally rely on our own intuition as to what might be the most effective method in the current situation. An important part of communication is the ability to address people effectively. The entrepreneur must have people management skills, in a positive sense. You need to be able to identify the needs of your customers and your team, your company, to choose the most appropriate staff to work with, to decide which of the investment opportunities to accept, who to vote for.

Flexibility and change management skills should not be separated from self-confidence and self-control. Effective change management will make all the difference for entrepreneurs who want to thrive in the 2020s business environment, adaptability is an important key to success. It can be said that the practical implementation of true self-reliance in our business is a leadership style that represents a level of commitment and the forms of communication that respond to the "here and now", that is the ability to reinvent.

Training exercise: *Internet research to collect from participants what combination of skills characterizes well-known leaders (Elon Musk, Steve Jobs, etc.), how they are reflected in the implementation of their ideas, in their businesses, in the material they are seen with.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers, wi-fi connection*

To be able to develop the soft skills that are important to us, which we think we need, is learning and using knowledge. The basis. Every entrepreneurial process is different, but the key feature is that you need to play a key role and use your knowledge to make decisions using experience, skills and intuition. You also need to be alert to market trends and developments and therefore rely on lifelong learning to ensure that your knowledge does not become obsolete.

Block 2 - Creativity

Creativity is needed, in small and big ways, because starting from an idea, from "nothing" and even with little to "no money", it takes imagination in every detail to start working towards your goals. In addition, changes in practice require a lot of imagination to face up to the various unexpected challenges that may arise. There is a particular value in someone who can add value to their project, someone who can make an attention-grabbing proposal, someone who can think in alternative ways to the usual, and who can be enthusiastic about it and infect others with this drive.

Creativity in the world of startups is best described as "Think outside the box", so that we don't just think in terms of design. This business English slang term is not used here primarily in its original meaning, thinking outside the box means coming up with new ideas, using new approaches, seeing things differently from others.

Training exercise: *Participants work in groups of five or close to five. The task is to come up with marketing ideas for the "Giovanni's" spaghetti factory. The factory offers a 1.5 km long but only 30 cm wide piece of land for the campaign. The task of the participants is to use this land in as many ways as possible to present and promote the spaghetti factory, using as many creative solutions as possible. The teams will write down the ideas they have collected on a flip chart, draw them and present them to the group at the end.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

If planning and organization emerge as a competence, do not confuse busyness with productivity and efficiency. Everyone has had experiences of spending days intensively working, writing or going from meeting to meeting, but at the end of the day feeling that they had not achieved any real results. It's easy to fall into this trap and that's why it's so important to work on your personal productivity, to be able to optimize the use of your time, energy and activities.

There are a number of soft skills that support planning and organization, but it is worth analyzing strategic, analytical, and conceptual thinking.

The ability to think strategically or to orientate takes on significance when we talk about the need for entrepreneurs and organizations to maintain a dynamic environment by developing and following continuous strategic change. It comes to the fore when their survival depends on their ability to innovate their models, to rethink flexible responses to market forces. As this is primarily a people-dependent process, entrepreneurs are the drivers of

of the change process, they are the ones who make strategic decisions based on their beliefs, their perceptions of the economic and social environment, their business portfolio and the state of the organization.

Analytical thinking is the ability to understand and solve situations, to solve problems by breaking down their components in a logical and systematic way. It is this technique, this type of thinking, that makes it possible to improve the quality of analysis in any aspect of any professional activity, providing those who use it with an advantage that is visible in the effectiveness of the results achieved. They are also a quick and efficient way to improve our agenda and time management.

Conceptual thinking is the application of creative, conceptual or inductive reasoning to existing concepts or to define new concepts. Conceptual thinking is understanding a situation or problem by putting the pieces together to determine to establish completeness.

Block 3 - Learning from feedback

The ability to work in a team and collaborate with others is essential, the team is the key to getting a project off the ground and running successfully. It is not easy to determine the value of an idea, often even for professionals with a lot of experience and business expertise in this area. However, a good team, a competent and determined implementation company, is definitely of great value, they can go further even if the original plans have to be thoroughly redesigned, almost completely changed or even completely rethought based on a partial idea.

Training exercise: *The participants have to collect where they have practiced these, how they have received feedback that they are good in these areas. What was their motivation to practice those skills? It is part of their portfolio and we will use it in the future process.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Confidence can be the key to entrepreneurial success! If you are confident in yourself, your team, your idea and your ability to achieve the goals you have set, you can really show this to investors, customers and communities. When we talk about being able to build confidence, it means that you believe that everything will work out, that despite the fact that there is room for error and success is the most likely outcome. Confidence is self-control, without self-discipline you can easily collapse, break momentum and become discredited. You need to be able to adapt to changing environments and challenges in times of difficulty, to be able to withstand adversity. The increasingly common term in this context is resilience.

In psychological terms, resilience is the ability of a person to recover quickly from unexpected, stressful or difficult life situations, or physical and mental suffering. One of the most important capacities of the twenty-first century human being, its importance cannot be overestimated when we talk about maintaining or improving mental health, coping with and recovering from difficult situations in life.

"It's not what competences you have, but how you combine them"

A potential entrepreneur needs to combine courage with openness, while being able to cope well with the pressures that come his way. How do the soft skills needed for entrepreneurship differ from the managerial competences essential in a corporate - "multinational" - environment? Many popular training materials and podcasts by influencers talk in general about the soft skills needed to lead people, manage clients, negotiate, and the importance of developing them. It's important to distinguish how it's different if you have to start, manage and develop your own business.

Training exercise: *They will have to throw a ball of unknown weight from a distance, which they are also not familiar with at the start of the exercise. In the first round, everyone in the team must say how many of their three possible throws they want to make from short distance - worth 3 points - , how many from medium distance - worth 4 points and how many from the longest distance - worth 5 points. The team with the most points at the end of the round wins. In the next round, they can discuss together what distance they will shoot from*

based on their experience so far, this is an opportunity for team members to give each other feedback and coordinate their roles. At the end of the exercise, the participants discuss their experience of what it was like to take on responsibility with unfamiliar conditions and how it differed from when they had the opportunity to discuss the conditions with the team members and know the conditions better.

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers, 3 type of small balls, a paper basket - steel*

We've already seen why being a credible, transparent person is important for your product or service and why it's a key factor for successful and challenged leaders today.

An entrepreneur, start-up or idea implementer must be prepared to be a leader for his or her employees. As this aspect has already been raised, it is important to be aware of how you will be able to handle this situation. A manager at the end of the first quarter of the 21st century should be a leader, not a boss, knowing that the more his employees trust him, the more they like him and the more likely they are to want to work for him. A leader does not want to be someone who forces employees to work, but someone who empowers them, who gives them a reason to work other than a salary. He wants to make sure that his employees know that he is trying to make a difference and that as a team they can achieve great things. Be their leader, not someone who bosses them around.

The competency to master learning is increasingly important for an entrepreneur and startupper because of the ever-changing challenges. You need an ever-renewing technical knowledge base with a focus on selling.

Soft skill: Innovation - Organizational skills - Business planning (MODULE 3-4)

Millions of people are thinking about which option would be worth pursuing, they keep coming up with ideas, but the key difference is which one will be successful in implementation. Which one of an entrepreneur's own ideas or those of others ancestors can be implemented is based on talent and training. "An idea, from an entrepreneurial perspective, is a business idea to produce products or provide services that can be sold in the market."

- How many hours (minutes) do you complete the given unit: 8 hours

Module 1 - A	Ideas and opportunities
Block 1 title	Transforming ideas into opportunities
Block 2 title	Innovation management
Block 3 title	Decision-making models and processes
Module 1 - B	Business planning
Block 1 title	Business Model Canvas I.
Block 2 title	Business Model Canvas I.
Welcome Note	<p>Welcome!</p> <p>In this module we will learn how software skills and their development contribute to turning an idea into an innovation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does an idea evolve from a social need? - Why should we consciously focus on organisational skills? - What models can be useful for design and implementation? <p>Enjoy the module!</p>
Task 1 - Title	Skills for innovation and planning
Task 1 - Instruction text	There are many places to look for good ideas. Some people swear by keeping their eyes open, stumbling across business opportunities along the way. Others think they can draw a

	conclusion for the whole market from their own unmet needs.
Task 1 - Links (if needed)	Finding the idea and the way to implement it
Block 1 - Resources	

Ideas and opportunities

Block 1 - Transforming ideas into opportunities

The Maslow hierarchy can bring you closer to a successful idea. We need to understand that individuals have different preferences, at different levels of the consumption hierarchy. In addition to looking at the needs of the individual, STEEP analysis, i.e. an analysis of the social, technological, economic, environmental and political (STEER) environment, can also be effective. It is a method for a systematic overview of the macro-environment around us, usually applied for a specific purpose, but it can also be used to understand trends and tendencies around us and thus generate ideas.

In order to use our creativity in the right direction, to apply it to the realization of our ideas, to the development of our business, we need to assess what our options are and what risks we need to be prepared for. We need to make the decisive assessments:

- Opportunity analysis and process definition
- Monitor and exploit business trends - Benchmarking studies and competitor analysis
- Growth orientation - Analysis of the development and learning processes that are absolutely necessary for scaling
- Goal orientation - Examining the short-term goals we strive for in a performance situation
- Stress and uncertainty tolerance - Analysis of individual and organisational tools and options to help manage uncertainty
- Calculated risk taking - Identifying what financial, market and other risks we can take

Training exercise: *Participants will choose the most marketable ideas they like best and work together in small groups to develop the four to five ideas that get the most votes. Here they use the information they have learned so far:*

- *They form a team*
- *Identify the tasks of the team members, taking into account their strengths and soft skills*
- *They work to develop a marketable version of the idea by taking into account how team members can work together*

These ideas and teams will also be used in the next exercises and will be further developed by the participants.

Tools for the exercise: *Maslow hierarchy printed, Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Block 2 - Innovation management

Innovation management, or innovation governance, encompasses all the activities necessary for continuous innovation, regardless of the size or other characteristics of the organization, and is a complex task, with several important areas to be kept under control at the same time. The ability to flexibly keep pace with continuous change and, increasingly, to respond to change in a timely manner is a key factor in sustained business performance. Another important factor is the ability to seize and exploit new technological opportunities and the (customer) needs that arise in parallel. These require a high degree of openness, flexibility and creativity.

- The innovation management process
- General leadership in innovation management
- Supporting idea generation as a leader
- Evaluating innovation ideas
- Supporting the implementation of innovations (from idea to solution and from solution to result)
- Resource assurance and monitoring

Training exercise: *The group's task is to develop an innovation management process based on the principles learned during a simulation exercise. Participants work in small groups, each group having an individual remit. The descriptions assigned to the groups will include the circumstances that will influence the task during the process. Trainers announce changes at appropriate times, simulating social and market changes.*

Tools for the exercise: *Role and task cards, persona cards. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Sales / Coaching approach to development

In addition to a wide range of classical management theories and management styles, people are nowadays increasingly seen as the greatest asset, with a people-centred management approach coming to the fore.

- Challenging and re-creating our own success, our own luck
- A coaching approach to sales preparation
- A coaching approach to customer negotiation
- Deepening the connection - consciously applying the GROW model
- Storyselling - introducing a good idea with a good story

Block 3 - Decision-making models and processes

GROW modell

- Goal
- Reality
- Options
- Way Forward

In a broader sense, coaching process models can be understood more as a framework based on a systems approach. Rather, they serve as a structure that can be used in practice, helping to position the process underway, providing transparency on the "journey" that has been taken and the "journey" that remains to be taken. One could simply say that it helps to respond adequately in the right place and at the right time.

Goal

The first step is to define the objective of the process, which, depending on the nature of the project, can be long, medium or short term. For example, it could be the achievement of something, but it could also be the achievement of a key result, a number of small objectives or performance indicators. Somewhere, we can always talk about a kind of success, where the client's (and possibly the client's) wishes are fulfilled. At this stage, care should always be taken to ensure that the objectives set are SMART.

Reality

The second step is to identify the current, real situation. In this phase, we try to identify the situation and the circumstances in which our client currently exists in a factual and objective way, preferably free of any distortions. This can be understood as the starting point.

Practical questions to help you explore the current situation:

- What is the current situation?
- Why is this a problem?
- Is it a permanent or intermittent problem?
- Is it an ongoing problem, or is it an ongoing problem?
- Is it an ongoing or current problem?

Options

In a third step, we will collect the alternatives that could be considered as solutions. A real-life problem always has many solutions, even if we think there is only one or none. Experience has shown that it is usually useful to collect several alternatives, even if they seem unrealistic at first sight, because we often see examples of how such ideas can be made realistic and usable with a little modification. Here, brain-storming can be used in the process of idea generation.

A few practical questions to help explore the possibilities:

- What opportunities for change do you see?
- What can you do? What else?
- What are the pros and cons of the alternative?
- What would you do if you could act without constraints?
- What help or support do you need?

Way Forward

Choosing the most attractive alternative identified above, planning a concrete way forward. The task is therefore to draw up a concrete action plan to which the team is fully committed.

- Some practical questions to help you develop the action plan:
- Which option will you choose?
- What specifically will you do to achieve the goal, and when?
- And then what will you do?
- How will you rate your commitment on a scale of 1 to 10?
- How can you get support in achieving your goal?

SMART model

Goal setting is a constant in our everyday lives, whether personal or business. The SMART goal helps us turn our vague plans into tangible and measurable goals. It helps you define who, what, when and why you need to do what to achieve your goal.

Elements of the model:

- Specific
- Measurable
- Achievable
- Relevant
- Timely

By Specific we mean that the goal must be specific and relevant to our client. Any generalisation should be avoided and a personalised, well-defined goal(s) should be set.

Measurable - In some cases this is not difficult, you could say self-evident, but there may be situations where it is more difficult. In such a situation, or similar situations, it is difficult at first sight to think in terms of metrics, yet this can be achieved in almost all cases. To do so, it is first necessary to develop the appropriate indicators and metrics, through which measurability can be achieved, albeit indirectly.

Achievable - A goal that requires real commitment, something that can be achieved but needs action, which cannot be achieved with current capabilities. This provides motivation, which often means stepping out of our comfort zone.

Relevant - Actionable, achievable objectives that lead to the desired state. Goals that are appropriate to the client's person and circumstances.

Timely - No task is a task without a deadline. A timeframe must be set for the achievement of the objective - or sub-objectives. This enables us to see the goal more clearly, to judge more accurately where we are on the way to achieving it, how much more we have to do, whether we need to pull ourselves together or whether we can relax.

Questions to help you set a goal:

- What do you want to achieve?
- What specifically would you be satisfied with?
- Why is this important to you?
- What will be good about achieving your goal?

How will you know if you have achieved your goal?

Training exercise. We will also use the steps and aspects of the GROW model and the possibilities of SMART analysis.

The end result of the exercise will be the first concrete project plans, 3-4 page outlines, which will already include the plans in a meaningful way.

Training exercise: *Brainstorming exercise to assess the options during the GROW model. By introducing the brainstorming method, we also aim to familiarise participants with this tool for later use in their group work. The exercise will be used as an element of group work at a time that suits each group, fitting into the process.*

Business planning

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management and lean startup method for developing and documenting the business model of existing or new companies.

The Business Model Canvas is a visual modelling tool. A 1-page template is used to place information relevant to the category. This is typically done in short, concise, few-word texts written on post-its.

Classical business plans are typically 30-70 page written documents that detail the business environment, strategy, competitors, assumptions and financial calculations related to the business model of the company or project.

In contrast, the Business Model Canvas presents the key building blocks of a project on a single page. This makes it a much quicker, simplified and schematic model to put together. However, this does not mean that it is inaccurate or wrong. It simply means that its purpose and value lies not in the detail, but in the basic context. If there is already a flaw in the relationship between the basic elements, it is completely pointless to write a 50-page business plan for that project. In this respect, the canvas is not a substitute for the business plan, but precedes and complements it. Think of it as an executive summary of a business plan.

The model consists of the following nine elements:

- Value Proposition
- Customer Segments
- Channels
- Customer Relationship
- Revenue Streams
- Cost Structure
- Key Activities
- Key Resources
- Partners

Block 1 - Business Model Canvas I.

The canvas model is an enhanced version of the Lean Business Model, it builds a business enterprise from 9 components that summarise briefly and concisely the aspects of the project's operation and strategy. As the name suggests, it is a model designed to represent complex real-world relationships in a simple, understandable way.

Advantages of the Business Model Canvas compared to other models

- it can be created quickly
- but can be extended in terms of content at any time
- it is flexible
- its simplicity and flexibility make it a popular choice for start-ups
- can even be used for non-profit initiatives

This model was also chosen because it can be used for non-profit initiatives. Participants' ideas are likely to include a programme that is not specifically for profit, but for community purposes.

Training exercise: *Participants form working groups to work together on their own ideas. Participants who wish to work together can also form a group. Groups of at least 3 but no more than 5 people may work together. Their task is to create three elements of a model based on the chosen idea:*

- *Define the relationship between the value proposition and the customer - Here they are looking for the answer to what value or product they are giving to the potential customer or target group.*
- *They plan the channels through which they will be able to connect them - The channel is responsible for how the customer will first interact with the product or service. And the customer connection is partly responsible for how the value will be delivered to them again and again.*
- *This will enable them to plan the source and frequency of access to the customer's money as a result of value creation.*

Block 2 - Business Model Canvas II.

For startups, the term pivot is a well-known concept. The canvas side interpretation of pivot business model is quite simple: if one of the 9 elements of the model needs to be changed, it is a pivot.

This change can be a change in the value proposition. Or even to serve a new target group. Such a customer segment pivot. If, on the other hand, the revenue model changes from a one-off fixed-fee revenue model to a monthly fee pricing model, we can talk about a revenue model pivot.

The right side is the value-added, creative part. This includes value proposition, customer/target, channel, customer relationship and revenue. In other words, how we create value.

Just like the right side of the brain, which is responsible for the creative, value-creating tasks. In the business world this includes a company's marketing department, product development, business development.

In contrast, the left side of the canvas is responsible for rational, number-based decisions. It includes resources, activities, costs and partners. Just like finance, operations, controlling, IT and legal in a company.

And when there is a company debate about whether or not to launch a new project, similar questions tend to arise?

- Who is our target group, who are we selling to? (Client)
- What marketing channel will we use? (Channel)
- How will we make money from it? (Revenue)
- OK, who will do this? (Resource)
- How much will it cost? (Cost)
- What partners will we need to use if we can't do it in-house? (Partners)

So really the right and the left are fighting and struggling to balance each other.

And hence, canvas is not only about value creation, creative side can be designed. Take a development company: they work for months on a project, and then when it runs out, there are a lot of free resources that management wants to do something with.

Training exercise: *participants continue to work on the idea in the working group already in place, their task is to create the next three elements of the model for the selected idea:*

- *To produce value, you need to have resources to carry out the key activities, it is up to you to plan this.*
- *Engaging external partners to do the tasks if you cannot from the resources within the planned team. Benchmarking research will also be needed here to get an idea of possible service packages and their expected pricing.*
- *Planning the cost implications of the whole process. Balancing the items shown here with the revenue side to make it realistic to implement.*

Soft skill: Leadership, Management - Dealing with People (MODULE 5-6)

Leadership is a trait that we as entrepreneurs need to develop, because being a leader is about being able to influence and support others in carrying out tasks to achieve a common goal. Demanding and pointing the finger is easy, it is setting the example that is the task of today's leader that is difficult.

- How many hours (minutes) do you complete the given unit: 8 hours

Module 1 - A	How to become a leader - Role of leaders
Block 1 title	Leadership roles, management
Block 2 title	Management methods
Module 1 - B	Conflict management - Assertive communication
Block 1 title	Conflict management
Block 2 title	Assertive communication
Welcome Note	<p>Welcome!</p> <p>In this module, participants will learn about the skills needed to become an effective leader and how to develop management skills. We will look at the process of communicating effectively with people and managing conflict.</p> <p>The assignments shall help you to develop a good understanding for the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do the different leadership roles mean? - How to share and delegate tasks? - How to manage conflicts inside and outside the organization? - What communication methods to use when you need to improvise? <p>Enjoy the module!</p>
Task 1 - Title	Dealing with people and conflicts

Task 1 - Instruction text	To become a good leader, it is important to understand how conflicts arise and are resolved within the team, with your counterparts and with the market. You need to know the generally accepted assertive communication method that can help you through these challenges.
Task 1 - Links (if needed)	Became a leader and transparent person
Block 1 - Resources	

How to become a leader - Role of leaders

Block 1 - Leadership roles, management

Leadership roles are often differently nuanced in an established, internationally dominant large company or in a start-up, in the process of being scaled up. In the process of thinking about and becoming an entrepreneur, we need to know both sides and understand the full spectrum of the scale between them, so that we can plan appropriately for our own and our peers' roles.

In order to be aware of the roles in which we can be most effective, it is important to know ourselves, our skills and our knowledge. However, as we develop both hard and soft skills, our perceptions of these skills may change. If we can see where we find our role within our company, we need to consciously build the competencies to do this.

Almost everyone in a startup wants to be CEO :) But let's take a look at what that means, what other roles there are and what you need to consider when dividing up responsibilities or deciding who to look for to manage those areas. Let's also examine what kind of soft skills are needed for the different roles.

The **CEO** is the first person in the company and the main decision-maker - that's why he or she has the greatest responsibility for important decisions, because it is the CEO who puts the final word at the end of the sentence in the life of the organisation. The CEO is responsible for the success of the company and is therefore also held accountable for failures. In order to make decisions, the CEO must be able to see the whole organisation at work: what is happening with the company's finances, the choice of staff, how the

organisation's marketing plan is working, what is happening in the research and development department, how the internal communication structure of the company is.

In the long term, the CEO's position is inherently part of the board, with an important role on the board and in management. The CEO is not necessarily the chairman of the board, but can hold both positions at the same time, and can be CEO. The CEO is supported by the heads of the functional areas, who are more involved in the day-to-day, practical running of the company. The larger the company (e.g. a multinational) and the more employees, the more the organisation is divided into units, with both smaller and larger bosses managing the employees - they may also make decisions, but they are responsible for each work stream to the person above them, ultimately the CEO.

To grow our business, it is important to understand that the position of CEO is often confused with that of owner. While it is common that the CEO often has an ownership stake (share option or some other arrangement), the larger the company, the more the CEO position and ownership are split and the more there can be a short-term conflict of interest, which is why it is important to align our ideas for development with our goals.

COO - The chief operating officer (COO) is a senior executive tasked with overseeing the day-to-day administrative and operational functions of a business. The COO typically reports directly to the chief executive officer (CEO) and is considered to be second in the chain of command. In some corporations, the COO is known by other terms, such as "executive vice president of operations," "chief operations officer," or "operations director."

- Depending on the CEO's preference, the COO often handles a company's internal affairs, while the CEO functions as the public face of the company, and thereby handles all outward-facing communication.
- Skills required to be a COO include strong analytical, managerial, communication, and leadership skills.
- There are generally seven different types of COOs that are best suited for different situations and different companies.

CFO - The term chief financial officer (CFO) refers to a senior executive responsible for managing the financial actions of a company. The CFO's duties include tracking cash flow and financial planning as well as analyzing the company's financial strengths and weaknesses and proposing corrective actions. The role of a CFO is similar to a treasurer or controller because they are responsible for managing the finance and accounting divisions and for ensuring that the company's financial reports are accurate and completed in a timely manner.

- The CFO is a financial controller who handles everything relating to cash flow, financial planning, and taxation issues.
- A CFO is often the highest financial position and the third-highest position in a company, playing a vital role in the company's strategic initiatives.
- Financial reports completed under a CFO must adhere to financial standards.
- People interested in becoming a CFO must have an academic and professional background in finances, economics, and/or analysis.

CTO - A chief technology officer (CTO) is the executive in charge of an organization's technological needs as well as its research and development (R&D). Also known as a chief technical officer, this individual examines the short- and long-term needs of an organization and utilizes capital to make investments designed to help the organization reach its objectives. The CTO usually reports directly to a company's chief information officer (CIO), but may also report to the chief executive officer (CEO) of the firm.

- A chief technology officer (CTO) is an executive who is responsible for the management of an organization's research and development (R&D) as well as its technological needs.
- Depending on the company, a CTO may play one of several roles, including strategic planner, customer relations liaison, and overseer of infrastructure.
- Becoming a CTO often involves at least 15 years of IT experience, along with a graduate degree and certifications in computer sciences and business administration.

CSO or CISO - The term chief security officer (CSO) refers to a company executive responsible for a company's physical and digital. This means a company's CSO is in charge of securing its personnel, physical assets, and information. As such, CSOs typically take care of online safety protocols, risk management, and responding to security incidents. The importance of this position has increased in the age of information technology due to the dangers of hacking, ransomware, and data theft.

- A chief security officer (CSO) is an executive responsible for the safety and security of company data, personnel, and assets.
- CSOs are responsible for preventing data breaches, phishing, and malware, by developing robust safety protocols and crisis management.
- These executives may also be responsible for physical security, such as preventing trespassers and protecting physical assets.

- Some tech companies may have a chief information security officer instead of a CSO, reflecting their focus on cybersecurity.
- CSOs are increasingly in demand, due to the specialized nature of their skill set.

Training exercise: *Project teams should have a meeting to develop their ideal imaginary leadership team. To do this, they use the individual soft skills they have previously gathered, who is strong at what and the results of the Belbin group dynamics test.*

Tools for the exercise: *Notes from previous training exercises. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Block 2 - Conflict management - Assertive communication

Conflict and the process of conflict resolution

Unresolved and unresolvable conflicts in a workplace, within a community, have a serious impact on organisational performance and often lead to serious losses in revenue and company image. If managers and employees fail to manage conflict appropriately, its negative effects will have long-lasting repercussions at the group and individual levels. The impact of this negative and accumulating workplace stress is the most destructive factor in our daily lives. The loss of GDP caused by workplace stress, and at European level this amount exceeds € 500 billion. The short-term effects are irritability or depression, fatigue, impatience, instability, anxiety symptoms. In the long term, mistakes multiply due to lack of concentration and staff are easily distracted. Communication is one of the most important aspects of conflict management, as it is the function of communication to establish and maintain contact and exchange information. It is precisely in these areas that conflict causes defects. The relationship changes and is damaged as a result of the conflict, and the distortion of communication is a symptom of this. Communication can also be at the root of the conflict itself, which can be addressed by using the tools of assertive communication. Conflict situations can arise within the organisation, just as conflict situations can arise between

Collaborative methods of conflict management can help not only to manage tension immediately, but also to maintain a stable positive situation in the long term. We have chosen a method for the organisation that can be used with or without a mediator if necessary. This is intended to be equally applicable when dealing with organisational or client conflicts that arise, depending on whether the parties involved require the involvement

of this third party. The steps of Daniel Shapiro's conflict management concept place great emphasis on recognising and managing one's own and others' emotions. Steps:

- Recognizing the conflict. Recall how you have felt in past conflict situations - role play, situational exercises.
- Our feelings. Examining our emotions What do I feel? Why? What does the other person feel? Why?
- What are we trying to achieve? Exploring our own and each other's basic needs Identify the needs of both parties. Jointly summarise regularly recurring situations in the work environment and in client relationships, and develop "routine" solution templates.
- Our ideas. Explore possible solutions to the conflict.
- Our plan. Identification and mutual acceptance of a solution that satisfies the core interests of both parties. Selection, agreement, implementation.

The Customer Experience Survey shows that 26 percent of customers would be willing to pay up to 10 percent more than the market average if providers offered a higher customer experience. In the same survey, business leaders indicate that they believe that companies that do not provide a high level of brand-consistent customer experience could lose 21.2 percent of their revenue.

The customer experience is defined as the customer impression that is created at all touch points in the customer journey as a result of the rational and emotional, conscious and subconscious influences that they experience. For most business segments, especially banking, insurance, retail, telecommunications, hospitality and public services, delivering a high customer experience has become one of the most important business objectives.

Customer management processes - user experience, organisational development must be designed in such a way that the tools, methods and results they achieve make the organisation self-learning about customer management.

Stress management and burnout prevention

- Working to particularly complex rules and instructions
- When decisions have to be made on the basis of incomplete information, are difficult to understand, or in complex, new situations
- Distracting stimuli that take concentration away from the work (frequent phone calls, clients, etc.)
- Dealing with a series of problems in rapid succession
- Particularly heavy responsibilities (financial responsibilities, decisions and tasks that seriously affect people's lives)
- Monotonous, repetitive action (routine but complex administration, similar cases)
- Work requiring a particularly high level of attention or patience

Persona development

The persona is a great tool not just for branding and marketing activities but to prevent the conflict with the target group, users. A customer persona is an approximate fictitious profile that attempts to define the average customer. It is usually based on market research data, where available and budgeted. The more elements you include to create a complete profile, the better, because the more accurate a calculation you can make. This includes demographic data, your customers' life goals, daily routines, motivations, the goals that drive them, their lifestyle and their behaviour in general. Generally speaking, the more detailed the better, which of course means the more time and money you have to invest in surveys.

The persona is what helps us to build a clear picture for our business of who our products and services are targeting, how they make decisions. Since in most cases this cannot be a completely narrow group, there are several types of personas to target, so we usually need to develop several personas and create a common picture that forms a cross-section of our target market.

By providing a human focus to your business, buyer personas help you get a feel for your customers. This in turn allows you to make business decisions that best help you serve your customers.

If you are looking for a checklist of customer personas, they usually include the following information:

- Residence
- Age
- Gender
- Education
- Occupation
- Income, savings, financial situation
- Family status
- Motivations
- Daily problems, challenges
- Shopping habits
- Hobbies

Ethnicity and religion are usually included in this list, but this now raises serious ethical questions and is worth serious consideration.

Training exercise: *Work out of a persona. In the project working group, the participants develop the target group of their planned service or product and identify the fictitious person or persons who will use it. If this is several different groups, they will create several person zones and a common cross-section of them. The description should include at least the aspects that have been presented in the list. This persona will be use for the branding and marketing planning later too.*

Tools for the exercise: *Empty persona cards. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Block 3 - Assertive communication

Assertiveness and Assertive communication

Assertiveness means expressing your point of view in a way that is clear and direct, while still respecting others. Communicating in an assertive manner can help you to: minimize conflict. control anger. have your needs better met.

Assertive communication could easily be confused with other forms of communication. In this section, we will learn what are the differences between assertive communication from aggressive and passive communication.

Aggressive communication occurs when a speaker is concerned with only their perspective and personal goals rather than considering those of their listener. Individuals who exhibit aggressive behavior are often focused on reaching their goals immediately without considering possible long-term negative consequences. While aggressive communicators might succeed in having their voices heard, they also alienate those around them and negatively impact their own success in the long haul.

Passive communication occurs when an individual doesn't voice their own perspective, feelings, or needs and routinely conforms to the preferences of others. Unlike aggressive communicators, passive communicators consider the potential consequences of their communication style but end up sidelining themselves for others. Research suggests that passive communicators might end up feeling depressed, helpless, and tense as a result of their communication style.

Assertiveness in communication is the ability to directly state your feelings and needs in a respectful manner. An assertive communication style neither shrinks from speaking up nor aggressively forces a perspective on someone else. Assertive communication is directed by the followings of effective communication:

- Be clear: you communicate in a straightforward way that directly states your thoughts and feelings without dressing up your language.
- Be consistent: what you say today reflects what you said yesterday, rather than changing daily without explanation.
- Be courteous: you respect your listener and communicate in a manner that doesn't pass judgment on them or presume ill-intent.

By maintaining clear, consistent, and courteous communication, assertive communicators can speak up and voice their perspectives without disrespecting others.

How to be assertive in communication: tips and examples

Assertive communication is all about getting your point of view across to others without causing conflict. While every situation is unique, there are some consistent methods you can use to maintain respectful assertive communication with others.

Scenario	Aggressive response	Passive response	Assertive response
A friend shows up late to a movie you really wanted to see, causing you both to miss it.	“You are always late and never think about anyone else but yourself!”	“It’s fine. I didn’t want to see it that much anyway!”	“I’m really disappointed we missed the movie because I really wanted to see it. Next time, I’d like us to pick a time that works better for your schedule.”
A person cuts ahead in a line you have been waiting in.	“What’s wrong with you? I’ve got to be somewhere!”	“Don’t worry about it!”	“Pardon me, but I have been waiting in line for a while and have to be someplace soon. Would you mind waiting your turn?”
A friend expects you to pay for dinner for the second time in a row.	“I always have to pay for you! All you ever do is take!”	“I’ve got it, don’t worry.”	“It frustrates me that I am paying for dinner again because I have been running low on cash. Next time, I’d appreciate it if you paid for us.”

Use “I” Statements

“I” statements are a form of communication in which the speaker describes their own beliefs and feelings rather than attributing motives to a listener. The opposite of “I” statements are “you” statements, which shift blame from the speaker to the listener through accusatory language.

A common formula for “I” statements is:

“I feel ____ when ____ because _____. What I need/ want is _____.”

For Instance, “I feel sad when you don’t call me back because I would like to hear from you. Could you let me know the best time to talk?”

Using “I” statements allows you to diffuse tension with a listener by offering insight into your internal feelings. This can help the listener see how their actions made you feel and redirect their focus on solutions, rather than projecting accusatory motives for their actions that only further heighten tensions.

Stick to the facts

When disagreements arise, conversations can occasionally get heated and veer off course. To help keep things civil when you are voicing your perspective to another person, focus on the facts at hand rather than letting your feelings cause you to speculate about the other person’s motives.

In keeping attention on the facts, you focus the conversation on things that can be handled at the moment and work towards solutions that benefit everyone. At the same time, keeping your focus on what you know to be true helps minimize the negative emotions that can arise from speculating about another person’s motives.

Be aware of your body language

Another aspect of how others receive your communication is through your body language. Do you close yourself off and turn away when someone is talking to you or do you open up and give them your undivided attention?

To embody assertive body language, stand tall in a straight but relaxed way, maintain eye contact, and keep your body open with uncrossed arms. Showing interest with an open demeanor will highlight both your respect for them and yourself.

Learn to say “No”

It can often seem much easier to say “yes” to more responsibilities than to decline someone’s request for help – even when you know you have other concerns that require your attention.

In fact, saying “no” to more responsibilities is sometimes the best thing we can do for ourselves and our employers. A good way to decline someone’s request is simply to say “no” and offer a brief explanation for why you can’t help. If the other person attempts to push the issue further, simply tell them “sorry” and reiterate that you don’t have the time. In some cases, you may also be able to redirect them to another person or an external resource that you feel might be able to help.

Maintain a calm tone

The way you communicate a message is often as important as the message itself. As a result, it is important to maintain a calm tone of voice when you are asserting your perspective, feelings, or needs in conversation with someone else.

To communicate assertively, you should focus on maintaining an even tone of voice that remains calm and free of aggressive emotions. By using this technique, you will get your message across to the listener without exacerbating any possible tensions.

Training exercise: *The group plays out situations in pairs, based on the situation cards distributed, and they are randomly assigned conflict management and communication styles to solve them.*

The rest of the team observes the process and gives feedback at the end of the process on how the communication could have been adapted to end up as a win-win situation.

Tools for the exercise: *Situation cards, communication method cards. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers.*

Soft skill: Communication skills - Negotiation - Pitching / Marketing (MODULE 7-8)

Communication is the glue that binds human relationships and societies together, and it is as old as humanity itself. As the ages have changed, so have the specific characteristics of communication. There are many differences between the communication of early man and man today, or between a medieval and a modern communication situation, but regardless of historical time and place, all can be described by a general model.

- How many hours (minutes) do you complete the given unit: 8 hours

Module 1 - A	Negotiation
Block 1 title	Communication basics and negotiation techniques
Block 2 title	Pitch and other presentation methods
Module 1 - B	Marketing and Social Media Communication
Block 1 title	Marketing and related soft skills
Block 2 title	Branding - Web 2 to Web 3. transformation and its effects
Welcome Note	<p>Welcome!</p> <p>In this module, we will learn how to use communication soft skills for our marketing activities and negotiations. We'll look at the process to effectively use Web 2 and Web 3 transformation to our advantage.</p> <p>The assignments shall help you to develop a good understanding for the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the power of structured communication? - How to organize effective meetings and negotiations? - What does it mean to look at branding holistically? <p>Enjoy the module!</p>
Task 1 - Title	Communicate, negotiate and show ourselves
Task 1 - Instruction text	The ever-changing, new challenges make it worthwhile to learn about the classical approach to communication, because traditional methods are changing almost daily, taking on new forms and channels. Another important aspect in business is that

	the Web 2 - Web 3 transformation is a mosaic, with different dynamics in different areas and target groups.
Task 1 - Links (if needed)	Become a master of communication and branding
Block 1 - Resources	

Negotiation

Block 1 - Communication basics and negotiation techniques

The Shannon -Weaver model of communication was the first to express that communication in the broadest sense of the term is the transmission of information, irrespective of the nature of the transmitter and receiver of the information and of the signal and code.

In communication, the main roles are played by the sender of the message, the communicator, and the receiver, who receives the message. The content and meaning of the communication is the message. The sender transforms this message into a signal, which reaches the receiver through the information channel. The operation of the transmitter often involves the encoding process. Similarly, the receiver performs the decoding. The communicator transmits the message in some kind of code and the receiver decodes it.

For communication to take place, it is essential that the messages are mutually intelligible to the participants in the process, that they understand the sign systems, symbols and codes used. Communication can only continue in a shared code. The behaviour of the receiver must respond to the signals of the code used within a short time.

A characteristic feature of the transmission process is that things are added to the signal which the communicator did not intend to produce. This noise often originates in the channel of communication. The way in which the message reaches the receiver is the channel of communication. Although not strictly related to the communication model, the communication environment or situation should be mentioned. This includes any external factor or relationship between the communicating parties that has or may have an impact on the communication.

From our point of view, the three most important aspects of communication are.

- Communication in the information-theoretic - cybernetic sense, i.e. information is transmitted in all kinds of systems.
- Communication in technical terms - information is transferred in man-made technical systems (telephones, computers).
- Social communication - information is transferred between people within the social sphere.

Training exercise: *The task is to conduct a negotiation based on predefined role cards, where the roles are to represent opposing interests. Based on the role cards, it is not clear which strategy they will have to adopt and they will work on the problem based on their individual characteristics. A good solution is to get to know each other's needs in detail and then it is possible to achieve a win-win outcome. The exercise is known as "Orange Farm" or "Ostrich Eggs" among the general negotiation training exercises.*

After the exercise, participants collect their experiences:

- *How did the partner behave?*
- *In what ways was it possible to gather information about his or her efforts (body language, tone of voice, etc.)?*
- *How important were the small details in our information material?*
- *What turned the meeting around?*
- *Who used what soft skills during the discussion?*

The observations are collected by the group on flipchart paper and used later in the discussion and to justify the theories in practice.

Tools for the exercise: *Printed role cards. Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Meetings and negotiation

Although each party has its own interests, the meeting is ideally friendly. At the same time, it is important to keep the meeting professional and polite. A cooperative, positive tone is more likely to lead to a mutually satisfactory outcome and even a working relationship that works well in the long term.

Business negotiation is a specialised communication process, a science according to some, an art according to others. But most experts agree that the skills needed to negotiate can be developed. This is important because the success of a company depends to a large extent on how effectively it handles such situations.

Negotiation is a negotiation between two or more parties within a set framework, without which the operation and management of a company is unthinkable.

It can take many forms, depending on the objective, but a common feature is that the parties want to assert their own positions in the process, and to do so they need to use a range of persuasive techniques and strategies. Ideally, both parties win in the negotiation, but the one that has been more successful in representing its own interests is usually better off. To become a true master of business communication, it takes practice and it is important to be aware of your own soft skills.

Preparation for negotiation should not be overdone. The more energy you put into this step, the better position you will be in during a meeting. For example, it is important to thoroughly research the other party, their previous agreements, the company's objectives, credo, products and services. It's also a good idea to think about the dynamics of the deal beforehand:

- Who wants to close the deal more?
- What alternatives are available to whom?
- What options does the other party have?

It is advisable to play out in your mind the likely course of the meeting, with particular emphasis on the possible reactions of the negotiating partner.

As long as the objectives of the negotiation are not fully clear, it is not worthwhile to enter into it. Part of the preparation is also an overview of exactly what you expect from the meeting, what outcome you expect, what you cannot give in to, and areas where you can make concessions if the move is made. All these will be important benchmarks to take into account during the meeting.

It seems essential that participants listen to what each other has to say, but in reality this is often where the process derails. If one is only concerned with what one is saying, it is easy to find oneself not understanding the other person's train of thought. Listening attentively also makes it easier to gain the trust of the person you are talking to, which is not a minor consideration when, for example, negotiating a deal or laying the foundations for cooperation. Asking clarifying questions, summarising what you have heard from time to time, not only helps you, but also reassures the other person of your sincere interest.

- Negotiation techniques can be improved.
- Characteristics of negotiation
- Preparation for negotiation
- Stages of a negotiation, Follow-up
- Characteristics of a successful negotiation
- The successful negotiator
- Negotiation styles, basic negotiation tactics
- Metacommunication, taking advantage of body language
- Reasoning techniques

Block 2 - Pitch and other presentation methods

A special negotiation situation is the pitch, deck or pitch deck, which is a presentation situation, but it is a quasi-negotiation situation, as you want to gain support from either investors or potential buyers.

A sales pitch is a condensed sales presentation where a salesperson explains the nature and benefits of their business, ideally in less than one or two minutes. Sales pitches are often referred to as 'elevator pitches' because they should be able to be delivered within the time constraints of a single elevator ride.

Salespeople are past the point of giving prospects hour-long presentations to sell products or services. Nobody has that kind of time and, to be honest, if you need an hour to relay your value proposition, you're doing it wrong.

They're called **elevator pitches** for a reason. Ideally, if you're giving me one, I should be able to understand what you have to offer in the time it takes to get from the lobby to my floor.

A good salesperson should be able to get their message across compellingly and concisely. If you can nail your sales pitch, odds are you'll have more time to talk down the line.

A product pitch is not much different than a sales pitch, but is specifically focused on a product or service. You'll go in-depth and emphasize how your product works, how it will solve their pain points, and the specific benefits it will bring to your customers.

As an example, a sales pitch can be broadly focused, like if you're a consulting firm that offers a wide range of services. You're selling your business as a whole, rather than a specific product or service, like a CRM platform or accounting tool.

The Sales Pitch Framework

If you have time to properly expand and work on a conversation, touch on points of interest. Here's a framework you can use for building your elevator pitch:

- **Problem:** Start with a statement or question about the problem you solve. You can present the problem using a personal anecdote, question, or eye-opening statistic. Answer the why.
- **Value Statement:** Share a very clear, concise statement of value. Be action-oriented and outcome focused. Avoid using jargon. Share benefits.
- **How We Do It:** Highlight unique differentiators and explain what you do.
- **Proof Points:** Provide clear reference examples and list recognizable achievements. Share industry validation and awards.
- **Customer Stories:** Share customer examples and successes. Tell emotional and personalized customer stories. Make it real and tangible.
- **Engaging Question:** Close the pitch with an open-ended question, creating a space to have a conversation.

Structure - How to make a sales pitch

- **Make it short.** - A sales pitch isn't a conventional presentation.
- **Make it clear.** - This ties in with the previous point. You don't have the time to go on tangents or talk about anything but the message you're trying to get across.
- **Explain who your customers are.** - Consider the picture you're going to paint in your pitch. Give your listeners perspective on who's buying your product or service.
- **Explain the problem they're facing.** - Cover why your customer base needs you. Your target market is only as valuable as the problems you can solve for them. Convey a problem they consistently face.
- **Explain how your product addresses their needs.** - You have to establish why they'd buy from you. What can you do better than your competition?
- **Describe what success will look like as a result of using your product.** - Show the benefits of your product on a broader scale.

When starting your pitch, you'll want to integrate the following essential elements:

- Start with the problem. Always start with the problem. Unless they know the problem you can solve, they won't be open to hearing how your product is a solution.
- Tailor the start of the pitch to their vertical. No one wants to hear a general pitch that would apply to any business. Research their vertical and use the information you found to personalize the pitch immediately.
- Offer stakes. If they don't solve the problem using your solution, what do they have to lose? You don't need to state it in such clear terms — but alluding to the risks at the start of your pitch can help you secure buy-in straightaway.

Start off a pitch with what you know best — yourself. While I don't think you should focus solely on yourself throughout your entire pitch, starting off with a personal anecdote can help you speak with more authenticity and foster empathy.

Ask a question that relates to the problem you solve.

Start with a stat that resonates and offers stakes. Starting with a stat can be effective — but it has to resonate with the audience and offer stakes.

Training exercise: *Participants will work in working groups to develop a presentation of their projects using the pitch methodology. They prepare and present 60-second and 5-minute presentations and then present them to the group. The group member will give specific feedback based on their experience so far. In practice, this means presentations of completed projects, which are also videoed and made available to the teams for future use.*

Ideas:

- *Tell a story.*
- *Include a value proposition.*
- *Personalize the sales pitch.*
- *Switch up your pitch.*
- *Practice your pitch.*
- *Try not to use metaphors.*
- *Create a WOW moment.*
- *Appeal to emotions.*
- *Back it up with facts.*
- *Tap into their fear of missing out.*
- *Educate them.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Marketing and social media communication

Marketing is an area where it is sometimes difficult to separate hard and soft skills, to determine which area requires which competences and knowledge. An important question is what is decided "by intuition" and how much is determined by data-driven decisions. In the case of online content, frequent changes in the algorithms used by service providers often require a professional or entrepreneur to make decisions based on their experience. At the same time, continuous and powerful societal changes - demographic, cultural, affecting content consumption patterns - in individual communication, negotiation, presentation, require us to trust our instincts, as this can not only help us succeed, but also to stay ahead of market trends.

Block 1 - Marketing and related soft skills

All marketing that produces content, publishes it and distributes it through different channels with the aim of attracting customers is related to the concept of content marketing. Information can be presented in a variety of forms. Including news, videos, reports, e-books, infographics, case studies, user guides, articles, photos, apps and more.

"The clear aim is to publish these and distribute them through different channels to attract customers."

There are many definitions of what content marketing is. The meaning of the term depends largely on the purpose and context. One of the most widely used definitions is that it is a generic term for marketing methods in which content is created and shared in order to attract and retain the attention of a well-defined and known group of potential customers, and thereby achieve profitable customer interactions.

The idea behind content marketing is that by providing high quality, relevant and valuable information to the target market, business results are achieved. This strategy retains and increases readership and improves brand loyalty - "consistently deliver high quality content that solves people's problems".

Content marketing is part of the online marketing strategy, the most fundamental part of which is copywriting. Content marketing is the creation of valuable and relevant content. It is created with the aim of attracting and retaining the attention of a well-defined target audience and then converting that attention into profitable customer interactions.

It is one of the most cost-effective marketing communication approaches today. It allows the marketer a degree of independence from the press. By using it, the information about your person, company, products or services that reaches potential customers is entirely at the discretion of others.

It creates content that potential customers and buyers find interesting. It addresses their desires, needs and interests, so it attracts attention without directly promoting the product, service or company. In practice, content marketing is not only used directly to increase purchases.

Companies:

- 82 percent of respondents want to use it to increase the visibility of their company and brand
- 74 percent aim to reach interested parties (lead generation)
- 71 percent aim to acquire customers
- 68 percent aim to be opinion leaders in the market
- 64 percent would like to use it for two-way marketing communication and dialogue
- 57 percent would like to strengthen brand loyalty and customer loyalty, and the same number would prefer to increase their website traffic.
- 45 percent of companies focus on using content marketing specifically to increase sales

Block 2 - Content development and management

- Inbound marketing

Inbound marketing includes all marketing methods that attract a potential audience. It therefore means engaging your audience rather than pushing your brand, campaign, message or products out to potential customers. For this reason, it is often referred to as 'pull' marketing, as it pulls the customer into your brand or sales proposition. Inbound marketing is often seen as a more authentic and organic way of interacting with customers and acquiring customers. This is because it does not focus on repetitive calls to action and generic marketing messages.

- Outbound marketing

Outbound marketing refers to marketing tactics in which a business actively seeks to approach and entice potential customers. This is often done with a mass group that has not been specifically selected or researched. It is therefore sometimes classified within marketing as a 'scattered' approach. However, this does not mean that it is a bad type of marketing, as strategic, top-funnel, outbound marketing can help reach people who can then be further refined through retargeting using inbound marketing methods. Remember, however, that outbound marketing alone often does not yield a high return on investment. You can probably think of brands that are known for regularly using purely outbound marketing methods - perhaps you've received the same flyer in your inbox too many times, seen the billboards, ads that pop up during a game or internet search. Without the addition of some strong and genuine inbound marketing methods, you could be missing out on a lot of opportunities and business with these tools.

Training exercise: *Participants will work in small groups to formulate inbound and outbound marketing messages on given topics for given groups, chosen at random. This includes circular e-mails, billboards, TV advertising, etc., as well as guerrilla marketing campaigns, PPC campaigns. Participants will present their ideas and the rest of the group will say what they think are the pros and cons of the idea, what other groups might be more effective or what changes could be made to make it more effective.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Planning and calculating the return on marketing costs

As in all business activities, it is important to maintain strict financial discipline and to base your actions on plans and expectations. In marketing campaigns, it is easy to generate losses by making a rash decision, as you can carry on with campaigns that do not pay off.

All project elements and investments should be preceded by a budgeting process, and this is of course true for marketing activities as well. By understanding how to prepare a marketing budget, we can help our business make the most of its investment and revenue. In start-up businesses, marketing processes can be much more complex than in traditional businesses, due to new technologies and frequent changes in internal regulations and pricing of multinational service providers.

The expected composition of marketing costs:

- team, labour
- advertising budget
- content production (including video and audio editing)
- software, subscriptions
- website development, maintenance
- other costs of social marketing campaigns

The ROI (return on investment) calculation - a financial concept with many uses - can be used to calculate the return on your online marketing campaigns. In this case, the ROI is the ratio of the cost of advertising to the profit generated by conversions (such as sales or leads). ROI can be considered in terms of immediate return (direct sales impact) and longer-term return.

Outline the user flow

Whether you are a PPC professional, a marketing strategist or a social media manager, the first step is the same at all levels: sketch the entire user flow with the client to see how many platforms the prospect is coming from and how this will meaningfully determine the cost, how diversified the communication is. How the customer journey unfolds until they reach the point of purchase.

Training exercise. The plan should include what inbound and outbound elements they plan to use, what forms this will take - written, video, image, audio - and how they can combine them effectively.

Training exercise: *The groups are working out a marketing campaign with cost planning and introduce their plan for the group as a last test of their project plan. The rest of the team observes the process and gives feedback at the end. .*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

Block 3 - Branding - Web 2 to Web 3. transformation and its effects

Branding - Conscious branding (branding strategy)

Every company and every product has a brand. The difference between market players is whether they make a conscious effort to build a brand. Many people tend to confuse the concept of branding with marketing. However, this idea has several pitfalls. For a business to succeed, the foundations need to be laid. The real marketing can only come afterwards. In this article we will cover the branding process and the basic branding tools.

This brings us to the definition of branding. Brand building is a conscious process of giving meaning to a brand (whether it is a product, service or company name). The purpose of brand building is to make our brand easily identifiable and to give consumers a reason to choose us from the myriad of competitors. Part of the strategy involves choosing values and consciously overcoming the emotions that prevent people from buying (or employing or supporting). Our brand is also a promise to offer solutions to stakeholders' problems and build loyalty towards our product.

Of course, brand building is not only emotional and psychological, but also has legal (e.g. trademark) and practical dimensions (image, appearance, advertising). However, the first step is always to define what makes our brand special and, ultimately, what values our business stands for. Without a sense of mission, it is not worth starting a business: if our sole purpose is to make money, it is easy to forget that economic activity is ultimately a social mission. The most important purpose of business is to solve customers' problems, and in doing so, of course, we also make a profit. Moreover, as entrepreneurs, we also have a responsibility to our employees and suppliers: as managers, we do the right thing when we seek the satisfaction of all those involved in the life of the company. Customers, partners,

suppliers, employees are all part of the equation, as is the production of shareholder value (profit).

Brand awareness and brand recognition

Brand recognition is part of brand awareness. It is the extent to which consumers can identify a brand without seeing its name. So it is based on the logo, slogan, packaging. It may sound silly at first to be concerned with such things, but there is a serious purpose to articulating the mission. All elements of branding and later marketing will be subordinated to the mission.

Identifying the values and distinctiveness of the brand is often referred to as the USP, which is short for unique selling proposition.

"What makes the product unique in the market and what extras does it offer compared to competitors?"

If it's a people-centred and personal experience, it needs to be communicated. If the product represents high quality, then it should be emphasised. Equally, price can of course be an advantage if the aim is to break into the market with affordable products. But be careful: the values attached to the brand are very difficult to change later. A cheap product is unlikely to become a premium brand.

The mission of a company can easily be eroded if we do not stick to our values. A good brand does more than just communicate through advertising: successful brands stay true to their values in everyday life. It takes a very long time to build a brand through conscious branding tools. But to destroy it, a single day can be enough.

To understand the transition from Web 2 to Web 3, we need to see the continuity of the Internet's history.

In the Web 1 period (1991-2004), users were passive users. Website owners created content that users consumed. Online content rarely changed, did not reflect daily activities, and sometimes did not change for years. This was partly due to a lack of expertise and a low degree of interactivity of the tools.

Web 2 (2005-2020). This decade and a half was the era of centralised services run by large corporations, where the money to be made on the web was made by big companies such as Google, Amazon, Facebook and Apple. Some call this the write-read era of the internet,

referring to the computer code that allows not only viewing files but also editing and opening them. Users can not only consume content, but also edit and produce it, which they can then publish on Facebook, Twitter or Tumblr, as well as other online forums and marketplaces. Although we had the ability to share content before Web 2 (think of the early internet forums), the rise of social media has taken this to new heights. The simplification of the process made instant content sharing available to the masses, and the masses were so large that the quantitative change over time led to a qualitative change.

Web 3 (2020-). If Web 2 is the read-write era of the Internet, Web 3 can be seen as the era of read-write-ownership: instead of using free technological platforms to share and consume content, for which we pay with our data, we can become active participants in the management and operation of protocols as users. We will not be mere customers and products in the eyes of large companies, but shareholders with a say in the development of technology.

Training Exercise: *During the simulation exercise, we will actively intervene to control when participants can provide feedback in the situations they receive, how they can do so, and occasionally interrupt them.*

Tools for the exercise: *Flip-Chart, Post-it - 4 colors, Blue Tech, Markers*

We need to incorporate the effects of Web 2 and Web 3 transformation into the design of our own branding and marketing campaigns and take into account the soft skills that we may have in our organisation and what else we may need.

Important questions to ask are whether a Google Ads or Facebook ads fit better with the strategy, whether there is a justification for building an Instagram profile, whether a LinkedIn presence is necessary, whether we need to cut into SEO, whether there is a large enough database to integrate email marketing into the communication strategy, and so on.

Many factors can influence the choice of tools and channels, for example, Google works on the basis that potential customers already know some information about the brand, while Facebook is mostly based on interest, so it is definitely worth starting to promote a new brand on that line.

Training exercise. In the case of external price requests, it is a natural phenomenon in the market to have as many professionals as there are offers: in principle, the costs of advertising and professional staff should be taken into account. It is therefore important to check here what exactly these offers include.

Closing

Test questions:

What are the really crucial differences between traditional businesses and startups?

- Startups are based solely on IT development.
- Traditional businesses cannot internationalise, they can only operate locally.
- Traditional businesses cannot get private - angel - investment.
- **Startups start in a highly scalable way.**

Why is it important for start-ups to develop their soft skills?

- Because if you can't fool investors, you have no chance of succeeding.
- **Because it's important to keep improving, to build an engaged team and to be able to reach customers effectively.**
- Because if we are not super creative, we have no chance of coming up with a secret idea that no one has ever thought of.
- Because, if we're not the best within our team, we're not the ones looking for the "big bucks".

Mik a Grow modell elemei?

- Going fast, Rude, Openig, Wild
- Goal, Reactive, Old school, Way forward
- Gathering, Roleplay, Opinions, Way forward
- **Goal, Reality, Options, Way Forward**

What is the Business Model Canvas?

- **A modern business planning model.**
- A tool for designing online communication.
- A modern CV format.
- A business return on investment calculation tool.

What is one of the most important tasks of a CEO:

- **To be responsible for the success of the company.**
- To ensure that the members of the organization feel satisfied and that all their wishes are fulfilled.
- To ensure that ideas are not stolen by other businesses.
- To have as much financial reserve as possible to buy up competing ideas.

What is the first step in conflict resolution?

- **Recognizing the conflict.**
- Showing that we are stronger and in control.
- Calling a secret meeting where only the CEO, CFO, CTO and CSO are present.
- Communicating online in an open letter that our company is struggling.

What is the acronym for STEM?

- **Science, technology, engineering and mathematics.**
- Scaling, teaching, engagement, management.
- Show yourself, tactics, emergency, meaningful.
- Sales, talent, engagement, mutual.

What is a Persona?

- A secret password used to signal teasing and hostile customers.
- **A customer persona is an approximate fictitious profile that attempts to define the average customer.**
- An AI-driven avatar of an organisation.
- A summary concept of our personal characteristics that helps us develop our soft skills.

What is the best description of a sales pitch?

- **A condensed sales presentation in which the salesperson explains the nature and benefits of their business, ideally in less than a minute or two.**
- A high-quality photo of your product that will convince customers.
- A calculation of our expected sales revenue for investors.
- A sales presentation in which the salesperson explains the nature and benefits of his business in as much detail as possible, for at least half an hour, but preferably an hour.

What is the relationship between inbound and outbound marketing?

- If you don't have enough capital, you can only use inbound tools, because you won't have money for billboards, for example.
- Outbound tools are outdated, only traditional businesses use them anymore.
- Inbound marketing is out of date, only outbound tools should be used anymore to build your startup.
- **After planning, it makes sense to take advantage of the opportunities offered by inbound and outbound marketing and combine them.**

